

**CREATION OF INFORMATION SECURITY POLICY IN ENSURING INFORMATION
SECURITY IN THE ORGANIZATION**
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE STATE ENTERPRISE OF THE INSTITUTE
OF HYDROGEOLOGY AND ENGINEERING GEOLOGY)

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Annotation. This scientific article provides for the creation of a mechanism for information security in the State Enterprise "HYDROENGINEERING Institute". Implement these standards in an organization's IT, using encryption algorithms, hash functions, and EDS through the security standards of the HYDROENGINEERING Institution. As a result, the HYDROENGINEERING Institution PC provides data and system security using system security standards.

Key words: information security at the enterprise, threats, unauthorized access, redundancy, information protection.

Introduction.

The State Enterprise "Institute of Hydrogeology and Engineering Geology" (hereinafter - the Enterprise) defines the goals, objectives and principles of information security in the field of information security policy (hereinafter - the Policy).

The company's activities are promising for the study, collection, processing and storage of hydrogeological information, the formation of a geofund of geological and other information on subsoil resources, a geofund of mining and geological materials, the identification of mineral deposits. compiling and maintaining a register of deposits and subsurface deposits. Minerals, cadastral information (state cadastre of deposits, demonstration of minerals and man-made minerals State water cadastre (groundwater), state cadastre of natural hazards, as well as zones of formation of new groundwater in the state cadastre of natural resources collects information and provides it to interested enterprises and organizations.

The company, together with interested ministries, enterprises, organizations and agencies, monitors groundwater resources, including groundwater, and conducts research on hazardous geological processes (landslides, erosion, karst), monitors their formation and development in mountainous areas.

The urgency of the issue is that the urgency of information security at the Institute is now a serious concern for its leadership in the field and requires the development of measures to prevent threats to information security through the development and implementation of appropriate policies. It is necessary to abandon the existing old system and develop a fully secure information system, creating a secure way to use the database through the Internet or the internal network of the enterprise. The management of the enterprise implements the implementation of this Policy by developing a clear system for addressing information security issues.

Scientific innovation: the availability of relevant information security policies in all organizations and enterprises today. It is known that on the basis of the policy, the basis of ensuring the security of data exchange in enterprises and organizations is established. In the selected enterprise, an information security policy was created as a basis for ensuring data security. In the security policy, tasks are defined in accordance with the structure of the enterprise's activities.

The main issues and hypotheses of the study: Today, in every developed and developing country, a large-scale work is being done to ensure information security in organizations. Therefore, the organization of information security in the selected organization is a key issue.

Results of research and analysis of scientific articles on the subject. Information security technologies can be divided into two groups, as described by A. V. Trunova in her scientific article "ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY OF THE ENTERPRISE":

Group 1 - protection of software and hardware for processing and storage of information from malfunctions, violations that may occur as a result of an accidental error;

Group 2 - protection of software and hardware of information processing from any intentional threats planned in advance by intruders.

Based on the above information, the issue was identified.

Problem statement: The main purpose of the chosen topic was to study all the processes related to the activities of the State Enterprise "HYDROENGEO Institute" (hereinafter - the organization), to develop an information security policy of the organization and to create a system of information security in the future.

Method of solving the issue: the systematic compilation of information security policies arising from the activities of the Enterprise.

Information security policy of the state enterprise "HYDROENGEO Institute"

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The Institute, together with the relevant ministries, enterprises, organizations and agencies, monitors groundwater resources, including groundwater, and conducts research on dangerous geological processes (landslides, erosion, karst), monitors their formation and development in mountainous areas.

The institute stores news, changes, scientific and technical information in the existing database. The existing database contains all the information of the institute. The database includes scientific articles, general research reports, relevant books and scientific materials.

The institute makes decisions based on the database of the existing system. Data breaches, blocking their use, or entering incorrect information can help reduce the effectiveness of decisions.

Widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the activities of the Institute, the creation of corporate information systems (CAT) based on them, the formation of geological and cadastral databases, as well as the creation of a single management system and remote access to databases, Internet access creates the preconditions for the emergence of information security. The computer on which the existing database is located is disconnected from the internal and external network, taking into account the possible risks to the data.

In this regard, the urgency of ensuring information security at the Institute is a serious concern for its leadership in the field and requires adequate measures to prevent threats to information security through the development and implementation of appropriate policies. It is necessary to abandon the existing old system and develop a fully secure information system, creating a secure way to use the database via the Internet or the internal network of the enterprise.

The implementation of this Policy will be carried out by the management of the Institute through the development of a clear system for addressing information security issues.

Section 1. General rules.

1.1. Areas of Legal Responsibility and Policy Promotion.

When writing a security policy, of course, the existing laws and regulations of the country are used. The institute also relied on a number of laws and regulations in writing its security policy. From them

Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About underground resources";

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About informatization";

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About electronic digital signature";

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "About electronic document management";

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 07.05.1993 № 848-XII " On the protection of state secrets";

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 8, 2005 No PP-117 "On additional measures for further development of information and communication technologies" Legislative acts such as Resolution No. PP-614 "On measures to organize the cryptographic protection of information in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the State Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan State Standard of Uzbekistan ISO / IEC 27005: 2013 were used.

In order to effectively address the tasks of information security in the existing system, the internal and external activities of the staff of the Institute responsible for the security system, the schedule of working days, functional responsibilities, psychological conditions, material and moral support studied and analyzed.

A necessary condition for security is a set of activities for the entry (exit) of individuals into the premises, work with information belonging to the Institute, storage and transmission of information, entry (exit) of documents and material assets, etc.

The policy and all the rules set out in it are binding on all employees, as well as those who work with information related to the Institute within the framework established by law.

1.2. Description of information security.

The main components of information security are access rights (integrity), integrity and confidentiality.

Access (availability) is the state of information and its carrier, which ensures that the user has unimpeded and timely access to the information intended for them. That is, to ensure the right to information available at the Institute.

Integrity is the state of the information (data) and the carrier that allows unauthorized or intentional destruction, tampering, evasion, theft, replacement of counterfeits, and alteration of the whole and its individual components.

Privacy is the state of the information and media that prevents unauthorized access to it or unauthorized access (copying) of documents.

1.3. Information security objectives.

The main purpose of the information security system is to ensure the sustainable operation of the Institute, its technical protection from unlawful encroachment, disclosure, loss, theft, tampering and destruction of information, production activities, including information technology protection against damage to vehicles.

1.4. Functions of Information Security.

In accordance with the stated objectives, the main objectives of this policy are as follows:

Formation of a set of organizational and technical measures to ensure information security;

Forecasting and timely identification and elimination of threats to the information resources of the organization, the causes and conditions that impair their normal functioning and development;

Creating a mechanism and conditions for rapid response to security threats and the emergence of negative trends in IP activities;

1.5. Principles of information security.

The principle of accounting for all events that occur during the creation, modification, access or distribution and storage of information is introduced to address the tasks of the organization and its structural units, including regional divisions. The following principles will be used as a basis for the development of this information security policy:

Complexity is the provision of security at all technological stages of their processing (modification) and use in all modes of operation of information resources.

Organizational measures to ensure the security of information resources include:

- ✓ Restrict physical access to information processing and storage facilities;
- ✓ Restriction of access to information through technical channels;

- ✓ establishment of access control rules, restriction of access to information sources and other elements of the data processing system through cryptographic closure of data transmission channels;
 - ✓ Copying of databases;
- Information security technologies are divided into two main classes:
- ✓ means of data protection from unauthorized access (data access restriction systems, antivirus protection, firewall, means of blocking data input and output devices, cryptographic means, etc.);

The timely conduct of activities is the active nature of security measures.

Legality. It includes the development of a security system based on the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of informatization and Information Protection and other normative acts on security, approved by state bodies within the framework of their powers, with the use of all permitted methods to identify violations and combat them.

Suitability the means and capabilities of Operational Protection must be justified and in accordance with the established requirements and standards at the level of modern development of Science and technology, from the point of view of this level of security. Specialized organizations that are most prepared for a particular type of security activity, with practical experience in the development and implementation of security measures and tools, should be involved. The use of technical equipment and the implementation of safety measures should be carried out by qualified specialists to ensure the safety of the IP organization.

Shelf. The means and capabilities of operation should be justified and in accordance with the established requirements and standards at the level of modern development of Science and technology, in terms of this level of security. Specialized organizations that are most prepared for a particular type of security activity, with practical experience in the development and implementation of security measures and tools, should be involved. The use of technical equipment and the implementation of safety measures should be carried out by qualified specialists to ensure the safety of the IP organization.

Dynamics. Based on its experience, it provides for the improvement of protection measures and tools, changes in methods and tools of intelligence and industrial espionage, the emergence of new technical means, taking into account regulatory and technical requirements, domestic and foreign experience. In addition, material facilities and the IP security status of the Organization are required to be maintained on a regular basis.

Section 2. Protected objects.

Objects that are protected from potential threats and unlawful attacks include:

Hardware is a set of electronic, electrical, and mechanical devices that are part of a system or network.

Hardware includes:

- computers and logic devices;
- external instruments and diagnostic equipment;
- electrical equipment, batteries and accumulators.

2.1. Information and information resources of the organization.

From a security point of view, the availability of an inventory and classification system for organizational resources allows to increase the efficiency of the information protection system, taking into account the large number of channels of unauthorized access to data. For example, the availability and potential use of modems on users' workstations is one of the most common ways to violate an information security policy.

2.1.1. Basic activity information.

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 20, 2006 No 27 "On approval of the list of state information resources, as well as state bodies responsible for their formation, use and support" and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 21, 2011 No. 1730 "On measures. On further introduction and development of modern

information and communication technologies" to form, use and support the following state information resources: function is loaded.

2.1.2. Information on the financial and economic activities of the organization.

Information on financial and economic activities is formed to address the following tasks: centralized management and control of financial and economic activities of the accounting organization with the possibility of maintaining several General Ledger; accounting for fixed assets and intangible assets; personnel management and remuneration; inventory management; procurement management; control over budget execution; cost accounting and operating expenses;

2.2. Software as a source of information.

The main part of information resources consists of practical, special and system software used to ensure the work of the Organization's KAT and solve its functional problems. These include:

operating systems (OT), database management systems (DBMS); special programs and systems for processing geographical data (for example, ArcGIS, MapInfo, etc.); programs for e-mail systems, interdepartmental electronic document management (E-Letter, E-Document); Office electronic document management software based on Lotus Notes and others;

Section 3. Access to information.

Differentiation of access to information related to the main activities of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 7, 2011 No 296 "President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 8, 2011" Additional measures to protect national information resources in accordance with the requirements of the resolution "On the implementation of the decision".

Organization of information access management. Free access management implements the strategy adopted by the organization to differentiate the use of information and is the basis of the Information Security Policy.

Responsibility for the use of passwords. Users should be aware of and follow the following passwords:

- keeping passwords secret;
- If passwords are not stored in a safe place, do not write them down on paper;
- immediately change passwords in case of compromise (disclosure or suspicion of disclosure of the password);
- select passwords selected in accordance with the basic rules;

Section 4. Category of information and information sources.

The bulk of geological and cadastral information is classified as 'confidential' and 'for official use'. In the process of implementing this Policy, a particular set of data should be identified by category (and by volume) through an inventory of geological and cadastral data and information resources.

Section 5. Information security threats.

Threats to information security are expressed in violation of the availability, integrity and confidentiality of information. The use of ICT achievements in the organizational system, the creation of local branches based on them, as well as their access to a single CAT, including Internet access, pose a number of real threats to information security. The analysis of information flows in the organization's system revealed the following characteristic threats to the organization's availability, integrity and confidentiality of information in the KAT area:

Violation of the integrity of information, software and other resources (tampering, replacement, deletion) in certain software tools used to create and maintain a cadastral database (for example, in the program ArcGis), as well as forgery of documents (counterfeiting) availability.

Section 6. Information security measures. Organizational activities.

Information security can be achieved through the following organizational and technical measures:

- identification of the division (department, group, service, etc.) within the committee responsible for information security;
- create its own EDS digital keys in the organization in the manner prescribed by law;
- regular training of employees in the field of information security;
- annual audit of information security in the organization and the resulting changes and additions to the Policy;

Section 7. Final rules.

This policy is not a permanent document, it is regularly reviewed (approved), taking into account the changes taking place in the organization, the introduction of new achievements of ICT and geographic information systems.

Conclusion.

In the first part of the research, the structure of the selected enterprise is studied. He was introduced to the types of incoming and outgoing data, the information exchange system. Threats and threats to information in the information exchange system have been identified. Types of threats are considered. Information security risk assessment criteria have been studied. The second part of the paper examines the main threats to information security. From them, certain types of threats were selected for scientific work, a list of them was formed, and a classification of each threat was given. Well-known threats come at different levels and in different directions. Based on these and similar characteristics of the threats, the selected threats were classified according to their behavior. Thus, a set of threats is divided into 9 classes depending on their behavior. For each class of threats, the problem of identifying and eliminating a threat is addressed on the basis of a list of threats. And, of course, methods, means and methods of protection against threats have been identified. The third part of the paper introduces the concept of security policy. I learned about the concept of security policy, how it is conducted, the types of attacks that can be proven in the databases available in the enterprise, the legal norms. Based on this, I have compiled a sequence of how to conduct security policy in the organization. As a result of the overall research, a security policy for the organization was written.

Resources used in information security policy development:

State Standards of Uzbekistan ISO / IEC 27001: 2008.

State Standards of Uzbekistan ISO / IEC 27002: 2008 Information technology. Methods of information security. Practical rules of information security management.

Normative-legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, normative-technical, methodical, manual and other documents of SE "HYDROENGEO institute". On the development of ICT.

The heads of structural subdivisions and heads of related state enterprises, as well as users admitted to the IT of the State Enterprise "HYDROENGEO Institute" are responsible for compliance and compliance with the requirements of this Policy.

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